

Variations of the Electrical Charge of Colloidal Particles.

Part III. The Influence of Non-electrolytes on the Cataphoretic Speed of Colloidal Particles and on the Adsorption of Ions by Colloidal Particles as indicated by such Measurements.

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In continuation of previous measurements (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **2**, 296; *ibid.*, 1927, **4**, 493) the cataphoretic speed of colloidal particles of arsenious sulphide as influenced by the addition of some non-electrolytes has been studied. Also the effect of hydrochloric acid and potassium chloride on the electrical condition of the particles has been studied in the presence of varying quantities of ethyl and methyl alcohols. Apart from their bearing on the theories which have been put forward to explain the process of coagulation these measurements have considerable interest of their own but a full discussion must await further investigation because our conceptions as to the nature of the so-called double-layer, the influence of non-electrolytes on the adsorption of ions and other related topics are yet unsatisfactory.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the Arsenious Sulphide Sol.

The sol was prepared by mixing equal volumes of conductivity water saturated with hydrogen sulphide and a solution of arsenious oxide prepared by diluting a saturated solution with an equal volume of water and then passing a current of hydrogen sulphide for a definite time such that a slight excess of arsenious oxide is still left. A current of hydrogen was next passed till the hydrosol was found free from hydrogen sulphide on being tested with lead acetate.

The sol was kept wrapped up with black paper in a dark place. The apparatus and method developed by one of us (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, 103A, 102) have been used. The same cataphoretic tube was used during this investigation. The tube had only two side tubes and the effective distance between them was found to be 4.2 cms. for both directions. The temperature of the thermostat was $35 \pm 0.05^\circ\text{C}$. The rates of migration per second per volt/cm. multiplied 10^5 times have been expressed after making corrections for the changes in viscosity and assuming that of water to be unity. The addition of non-electrolytes has been found to make reliable measurements more difficult as the boundary becomes sensitive to slight changes in the composition of the upper liquid: Taking necessary precautions it is possible to get results reproducible within $\pm 2\%$. The error involved in reading the position of the boundary increases at high concentrations of the non-electrolyte.

The upper liquid used was an equally conducting hydrochloric acid solution to which the non-electrolyte and the electrolyte, if any, were added in the same proportion as that in which they were present in the solution.

RESULTS.

TABLE I.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol¹ and Methyl Alcohol.

% of methyl alcohol by vol.	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	Relative viscosity.	Rate of migration corrected for viscosity $\times 10^5$.
0 (pure sol)	62.99	59.57	61.28	1.018	62.40
2½	56.45	53.33	54.89	1.048	57.54
5	45.63	45.63	45.63	1.091	49.82
10	29.09	33.98 (?)	31.54	1.155	36.43
15	25.64	26.75	26.20	1.242	32.55

The non-electrolyte added replaces an equal volume of water.

TABLE II.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol and Ethyl Alcohol.

% of ethyl alcohol by vol.	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	Relative viscosity.	Rate of migration corrected for viscosity $\times 10^5$.
0 (pure sol)	62.99	59.57	61.28	1.018	62.40
2½	55.45	55.46	55.45	1.062	58.90
5	51.52	47.39	49.49	1.126	55.72
10	41.45	41.55	41.50	1.258	52.20

TABLE III.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol and Urea.

% of urea by weight (gms. in 100 c.c.).	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	Relative viscosity.	Rate of migration corrected for viscosity $\times 10^5$.
0 (pure sol)	62.99	59.57	61.28	1.018	62.40
2½	55.08	55.19	55.11	1.043	57.62
5	46.21	45.76	45.98	1.050	43.31
10	40.02	42.29	41.15	1.080	44.38

TABLE IV.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol and Cane Sugar.

Cane sugar (gms. in 100 c.c.)	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	Relative viscosity.	Rate of migration corrected for viscosity $\times 10^5$.
0 (pure sol)	64.25	60.08	62.16	1.015	63.07
2½	48.59	46.53	47.56	1.054	50.12
5	31.03	30.59	30.81	1.119	34.49
10	24.81	26.56	25.83	1.263	32.64

TABLE V.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol and Acetone.

% of acetone by volume.	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	Relative viscosity.	Rate of migration corrected for viscosity $\times 10^6$.
0 (pure sol.)	64.25	60.08	62.16	1.014	63.07
2½	52.23	54.24	53.24	1.041	55.40
5	45.51	45.44	45.47	1.084	49.32
10†	—	—	—	—	—

TABLE VI.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol and iso-Butyl alcohol.

% of iso-butyl alcohol (by volume).	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	Relative viscosity.	Rate of migration corrected for viscosity $\times 10^6$.
0	64.25	60.08	62.16	1.016	63.07
2½	59.95	55.55	57.75	1.068	61.68

TABLE VII.

Arsenious Sulphide with Ethyl Alcohol and Potassium Chloride.

% of ethyl alcohol by volume.	Conc. of potassium chloride.	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	Relative viscosity.	Rate of migration corrected for viscosity $\times 10^6$.
0	0	60.70	61.56	61.13	1.020	62.38
0	.01 N	56.69	56.47	56.58	1.010	57.12
2½	„	51.89	52.90	52.40	1.062	55.68
5	„	46.18	46.68	46.43	1.121	52.07
10	„	39.65	38.63	39.14	1.262	49.40
0	.02 N*	53.46	57.39	55.42	1.006	55.78
0	„ *	55.91	55.18	55.54	1.006	55.90
2½	„ *	49.42	49.46	49.44	1.068	52.68
5	„ *	41.79	41.75	43.75	1.140	49.91
10	„ *	35.57	35.61	35.59	1.272	45.29
0	.04 N	53.37	51.91	52.64	1.017	53.53
0	„	52.87	52.72	52.80	1.017	53.69
2½	„	52.48	51.66	52.07	1.066	55.55
5	„	46.73	46.46	46.59	1.131	52.70
10	„	40.24	40.91	40.57	1.208	48.80

† The boundary gets disturbed during the 'reverse' movement.

* The pure sol used in these measurements showed a rate of 63.07×10^{-6} cm. per volt/cm.

TABLE VIII.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol with Methyl Alcohol and Potassium Chloride.

% of methyl alcohol by volume.	Conc. of potassium chloride.	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	Relative viscosity.	Rate of migration corrected for viscosity $\times 10^6$.
0	0	67.57	63.37	65.47	1.020	66.81
0	0	64.60	63.71	64.15	1.020	65.46
0	.004 N †	59.35	59.18	59.26	1.023	60.64
2½	„ †	51.55	52.38	51.96	1.051	54.60
5	„ †	43.12	55.16	44.14	1.081	47.71
10	„ †	30.64	35.32	32.98	1.188	39.20
0	.01 N	56.69	56.47	56.58	1.010	57.12
2½	„	54.90	56.70	55.80	1.042	58.15
5	„	49.88	56.54	51.72	1.084	56.08
10	„	40.99	41.04	41.01	1.160	47.60
0	.02 N	53.46	57.39	55.42	1.006	55.78
2½	„	57.25	60.78	59.01	1.046	61.71
5	„	52.49	54.64	53.51	1.076	57.60
10	„	46.70	47.89	47.30	1.156	54.69
0	.04 N	52.87	52.72	52.80	1.017	58.69
2½	„	60.08	61.69	60.86	1.066	64.91
5	„	55.90	57.16	56.53	1.077	61.65
10	„	44.76	51.34	48.05	1.171	56.29

† Measurements with .004 N potassium chloride was carried with a different preparation of the hydrosol which gave a rate of migration (corrected for viscosity) of 66.27×10^{-6} .

TABLE IX.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol with Ethyl Alcohol and Hydrochloric Acid.

% of ethyl alcohol by volume.	Conc. of hydrochloric acid.	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	Relative viscosity.	Rate of migration corrected for viscosity $\times 10^4$.
0	0	66.85	63.27	65.06	1.034	67.26
2½	0	55.45	55.46	55.45	1.062	58.90
5	0	51.52	47.39	49.49	1.126	55.73
0	.005 N	52.17	50.94	51.56	1.017	52.44
2½	„	46.51	47.51	47.01	1.069	50.22
5	„	41.37	42.72	42.04	1.121	47.14
0	.01 N	45.66	46.88	46.27	1.000	46.26
2½	„	41.88	42.48	42.18	1.069	44.98
5	„	37.02	37.54	37.28	1.113	41.52
0	.015 N	43.37	43.64	43.50	1.003	43.62
2½	„	36.97	37.65	37.31	1.067	39.80
5	„	30.46	31.84	31.15	1.131	35.24

TABLE X.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol with Methyl Alcohol and Hydrochloric Acid.

% of methyl alcohol by volume.	Conc. of hydrochloric acid.	Direct.	Reverse.	Mean.	Relative viscosity.	Rate of migration corrected for viscosity $\times 10^5$.
0	0	66.85	63.27	65.06	1.034	67.26
2½	0	56.45	53.83	54.89	1.045	57.54
5	0	47.73	45.79	46.76	1.091	51.04
0	.005 N	52.17	50.94	51.56	1.017	52.44
2½	„	42.04	42.48	42.26	1.051	44.40
5	„	37.14	36.64	36.89	1.081	39.87
0	.01 N	45.66	46.88	46.27	1.013	46.26
2½	„	41.37	41.06	41.22	1.042	42.96
5	„	37.16	36.03	36.59	1.083	39.67
0	.015 N	43.37	43.64	43.50	1.030	43.62
2½	„	44.87	44.70	44.78	1.045	46.83
5	„	40.04	41.06	40.55	1.076	43.64

DISCUSSION.

(a) *The Effect of Non-electrolytes.*

The effect of non-electrolytes on the pure sol will be apparent from Figure (I). Cane-sugar which has very nearly the same effect

FIG. I.

on the dielectric constant of the medium at these concentrations as the other non-electrolytes decreases the cataphoretic speed (corrected for the alteration in viscosity) considerably and urea which slightly increases the dielectric constant also lowers the cataphoretic speed. According to Helmholtz u , the cataphoretic speed, ϕ the potential of the double layer, k , the dielectric constant and η the co-efficient of viscosity, are correlated by the following equation:—

$$u_0 = u\eta = \frac{k\phi}{4\pi} \dots (1)$$

The potential of the double layer is proportional to u_0/k where u_0 is

the cataphoretic speed after viscosity correction. It will be seen that an increase or a diminution of the dielectric constant on the addition of the non-electrolyte produces the same effect, namely, a lowering of the cataphoretic speed. It is apparent that the potential of the double layer is not determined by the change in the dielectric constant alone as Freundlich has assumed (*Kapillarchemie*, 1922, p. 638). After referring to equation (1) he states "Ein kleineres D bedingt ein kleineres u." Evidently he assumes the potential to be constant. He further (p. 337) discusses the relationship

$$e = \frac{\phi \cdot k \cdot r \cdot (r + \delta)}{\delta} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where e is the density of the electrical charge on the surface, r is the radius of the particle and δ is the thickness of the double layer and points out that if the potential of the double layer remains constant and the dielectric constant decreases evidently, e the density of the charge should decrease, assuming that the thickness of the double layer is constant. There is no justification for considering that the potential will remain constant and the density of the charge will vary as the dielectric constant. This will be evident from Table XI to XIII below.

TABLE XI.

Methyl Alcohol.

% of Methyl alcohol	0	2½	5	10	15
k	80·4	78·75	77·5	75·0	72·8
u_0/k	·776	·730	·643	·486	·447

TABLE XII.

Cane Sugar.

% of cane sugar	0	2½	5	10
k	80·4	78·25	77·0	76·2
u_0/k	0·784	0·640	0·448	0·429

TABLE XIII.

% of urea.	Urea.			
	0	2½	5	10
k	80.4	80.0	81.0	83.25
u_0/k	0.776	0.720	0.596	0.533

The values k , obtained by interpolation from the data of Lattey (*Phil. Mag.*, 1921, 41, 829) and of Harrington, (*Physical Rev.*, 1916, 3, 581) have been used to determine the values of u_0/k given in the tables. It is obvious that the charge may be affected by other factors. There is evidence to show that a direct relationship exists between the amount of excess of adsorption of an ion of one sign and the rate of electro-osmotic or cataphoretic movements. It is therefore more rational to correlate the cataphoretic speed with the density of the charge on the surface of the particle. Lamb's equation has as its basis such a relation, if we assume that the facility of slip is not a function of the density of the charge. In Helmholtz's treatment also the fundamental factor determining the electrical force F is given by

$$F = H\rho \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

where H is the intensity of the field and ρ is the volume density of the charge. The potential difference at the interface is introduced by Helmholtz through Poisson's relation for facilitating the solution of the hydrodynamic equations.

We see from equations (1) and (2) that e cannot vary directly as u_0 unless δ is constant. Further that a proportionality between u_0 and e (δ constant) does not necessarily imply that both e and u_0 vary as δ .

Theoretical considerations make it plausible that if δ be a function of k then it will vary directly as k . In that case u_0 cannot vary directly as k as assumed by Freundlich unless e is constant. The fact that all the non-electrolytes mentioned above lower the cataphoretic speed cannot therefore be explained from the above point of view. It is more plausible to explain our observations by assuming that either the density of the charge is changing or preferably both the density and the thickness of the double layer are

changing. The great effect of cane sugar points to the conclusion that the variation in the density of the charge is the main factor. As our knowledge regarding the thickness of the double layer is insufficient it is not possible to discuss this question in greater detail. It is hoped that further investigations will enable us to form a clearer conception of the double layer.

(b) *Mixture of Non-electrolytes and Electrolytes.*

In this series of measurements the following broad peculiarities are noticeable.

Excluding the case of hydrochloric acid and ethyl alcohol on the addition of the non-electrolyte along with an electrolyte there is at first a marked decrease in speed but at higher concentrations the cataphoretic speed increases. In the case of potassium chloride at

Fig. II.

all the three concentrations of ethyl alcohol the curves are nearly parallel and the minimum speed is observed at a concentration of 0.02N of the electrolyte (Fig. II).

Methyl alcohol magnifies this tendency both as regards the initial decrease and the subsequent rise (Fig. III) and it is noticeable also for hydrochloric acid. The minimum in the presence of methyl

Fig. III.

alcohol and potassium chloride occurs at a much lower concentration. If we assume the validity of Helmholtz's equation in its usual form the cataphoretic speed u_0 is proportional to $K\phi$.

It is usually supposed that coagulation takes place at a constant critical potential which must be sufficiently low. We however find that on the addition of the non-electrolyte the speed rises considerably and in some case (*e.g.*, MeOH and hydrochloric acid) to a value greater than that of the original sol. Kruyt and Willigen *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 130, 170) have attempted to account for coagulation by electrolytes when the electrolyte increases the cataphoretic speed on the basis that the dielectric constant k rises with increasing concentration of the electrolyte and hence the actual potential is less than that for the sol without electrolyte. In the case of 10 per cent. methyl alcohol and varying concentration of potassium chloride, the cataphoretic speed increases from a minimum

of about 39 to about 56, i.e., by about 43 per cent. The dielectric constant of the mixture in the presence of 0.04N KCl must be supposed to be about 43 per cent. greater than that in the absence of the electrolyte in order to bring down the potential to its original value and if we assume that coagulation takes place at a lower potential (the critical potential) then the increase in the dielectric constant must be supposed to be much greater. It is most unlikely that the dielectric constant changes to such an extent and we conclude that there is no definite critical potential characteristic of the coagulation by an electrolyte as was suggested by Powis and quoted in the literature. Mukherjee and co-workers have repeatedly emphasised (cf. Mukherjee, *Thesis* ; Mukherjee and Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 296; Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Rai-choudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 493) that this postulate is not warranted by facts. It thus appears that neither the cataphoretic speed nor the potential of the double layer calculated as above has a critical value at the coagulating concentration. A more probable explanation may be suggested on the following basis. The cataphoretic speed is a measure of the density of the electrical charge and the stability of the sol is dependent on the electrical charge in so far as electrical work must be done in displacing the free ions in the mobile layer when two particles come very near each other. This electrical work is determined by the number of ions displaced, the shape and extent of the surface affected (which also governs the distance through which these ions are displaced) and the dielectric constant of the medium. These considerations though more satisfactory than the conception of a critical potential are not however sufficient, for, as we find, coagulation occurs at a much higher cataphoretic speed than can possibly be explained by an increase in the dielectric constant resulting from the presence of the electrolyte. One way out of this difficulty would be on the basis that the cataphoretic speed is proportional to the product of the surface density and the thickness of the double layer and to assume that the thickness of the double layer depends on the dielectric constant so that the density of the charge is much smaller than that represented by the cataphoretic speed. An increase in the dielectric constant will also diminish the electrical work, other conditions remaining the same as an increase in the dielectric constant will have a two-fold effect and it may be that the nett electrical work will be less than that for the approach of two particles of the original sol.

As we have no reliable data on the dielectric constant of so highly conducting solutions these considerations are not very useful.

On the other hand we know that ethyl alcohol and methyl alcohol sensitises the sol as would appear from the following data, from a paper by Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 349).

TABLE XIV.

Arsenious Sulphide Sol.

Percentage concentration of ethyl alcohol.	Electrolyte concentration in normality.		
	HCl	KCl	AlCl ₃
0	0.03800	0.05944	0.0002184
2.5	0.03675	0.06064	0.0002146
5	0.03525	0.06301	0.0002146
10	0.03400	0.07055	0.0002109
15	0.03300	0.07847	0.0002109
25	0.03500	0.00618	0.0002033

TABLE XV.

Percentage of methyl alcohol.	Electrolyte concentration in normality		
	HCl	KCl	AlCl ₃
0	0.04450	0.06024	0.0001995
2.5	0.04325	0.05909	0.0001957
5	0.04225	0.05863	0.0001920
10	0.04050	0.06707	0.0001882
15	0.03850	0.06470	0.0001770
25	0.02550	0.05070	0.0001581

The cataphoretic speed at an electrolyte concentration of .04N-KCl decreases with increasing content of methyl alcohol but the cataphoretic speed at the same electrolyte concentration when no alcohol is added is in this case the least. While the increasing sensitisation with the increasing concentrations of methyl alcohol can be explained by the progressive diminution of the cataphoretic speed such an explanation is not possible for the case when no electrolyte is added, unless we assume that the dielectric constants of the alcohol-water mixtures are considerably greater in the presence of the electrolyte than that of the pure aqueous solution. It is not possible to lose sight of the fact that the coagulating concentration cannot be directly correlated either to the potential of the double layer or the cataphoretic speed without introducing a number of assumptions, the validity of which remains to be tested. It is therefore desirable to keep in view the possibility that specific forces of the nature of cohesion may be operating and these are affected by the adsorption of ions from the electrolyte and of the non-electrolyte. The observations of Bhattacharya in this laboratory show that the manner of variations of the cataphoretic speed with the concentration of potassium chloride is different depending on the method of preparation of the sol and its dilution, but the coagulating concentration does not show an equally complicated behaviour. It therefore seems probable that in addition to the effect of electrical work and cohesive forces stated above, we have to consider that the actual stable aggregation results from a simultaneous entrainment in the surface of contact, of an equivalent (or nearly equivalent) amount of the ions of opposite sign in the mobile layer. This idea is similar to that underlying Whetham's attempt at an explanation of the valency rule of Schulze.

From the foregoing the complex nature of the observations and the difficulties of explaining them on the basis of the theories in vogue at present are apparent. Similar difficulties stand in the way of accounting for the cataphoretic speed from the point of view of the adsorption of ions. Broadly speaking we notice that the rise in the cataphoretic speed at higher concentrations depends on both the nature of the cation and the non-electrolyte. The marked initial decrease in the presence of the non-electrolytes may be referred to a lowering of the dielectric constant and an increase in the adsorbability of the cation.

The non-electrolyte has an effect both on the degree of dissociation (osmotic coefficient) as determined from conductivity measurements and on the mobility of the ion. On theoretical grounds it appears probable that the osmotic coefficient (and not the activity coefficient) is the relevant factor in these cases. On Debye's theory from considerations of the electrical factor, the osmotic coefficient should decrease with the diminution in the dielectric constant and hence the osmotic coefficient should be the least for methyl alcohol and the greatest for water. It is well known that the mobilities diminish on the addition of alcohol and the percentage diminution is very high for small concentrations of the non-electrolyte.

The slope of the curve showing the initial decrease in charge will be much greater if we plot the osmotic coefficients instead of the stoichiometric concentration. On the basis of Mukherjee's theory of electrical adsorption this increased slope can be accounted for by the lower dielectric constant which would increase the adsorbability of the cation. There is no doubt as to this increase in the adsorbability if one also considers the lower mobility and makes corrections according to his equation. Now the diminution in the charge facilitates the primary adsorption of chlorine ions which have an affinity for the surface of the arsenious sulphide particles (*cf.* Weiser, Dhar). On the other hand the rate of increase of the actual concentration of the cation with the stoichiometric concentration of the electrolyte is slower in the presence of non-electrolytes on account of the stronger electrical forces. If we also consider the lowering of the mobility of the cation on the addition of these non-electrolytes it is not surprising that the primary adsorption of the anions soon rapidly increases and hence surpasses the progressively weaker adsorption of the cation. The initial lower speed may be taken to indicate a lower density of charge and consequently the repulsive forces exerted on the anions by the negatively charged surface is smaller. This would moreover increase the rate of adsorption of the anion. Apparently these effects will be more pronounced the higher the concentration of the non-electrolyte and the lower its dielectric constant. Moreover for the same anion the lower the adsorbability of the cation, the more pronounced will be these features (the initial drop and the subsequent rise).

Fig. IV.

Fig. V.

These conclusions are fairly borne out by the Figures IV and V. While this representation enables us to form a picture, subject to the limitations mentioned, there is one difficulty. The osmotic coefficient of the chlorine ions and its mobility are also smaller. Besides the lower dielectric constant will decrease the adsorption of chlorine ions. It is of course possible that there is an increase in the dielectric constant with the increasing concentration of the electrolyte as is to be expected from the theory of Debye and Hückel. Further, as the adsorption of the chlorine ions is determined by chemical affinity it will be less susceptible to the electrical forces discussed above than will be the case with potassium ions whose adsorption on the above theory is only determined by these electrical forces. We thus see that it is possible to account for the complex manner of variations of the cataphoretic speed on the above basis assuming that the cataphoretic speed is a measure of the surface density and that simultaneous entrainment of the ions of opposite sign is necessary at the time of contact for stable aggregation. A connected picture, however vague of the process of coagulation, adsorption of ions and the electric charge, can thus be presented.

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